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<p>Abstract</p>	<p>This deliverable introduces the ACTION Participation Roadmap Tool', which outlines various strategies that citizen science projects can use to increase community engagement. We introduce six strategies, which can increase participation: self-efficacy, diversity and accessibility, social interaction between citizens, recruitment and project framing, appreciation and importance, and gamification. In addition, we suggest practical advice on how to implement these strategies in practice.</p>
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines/strategies and tools for community engagement and monitoring in citizen science. Based on a systematic literature review, interviews with citizens and project managers of a citizen science project, and feedback received during three workshops, we developed the ACTION Participation Roadmap Tool for the citizen science community. This Participation Roadmap Tool contains strategies as well as practical advice on how to implement these in citizen science projects.

Following these strategies is expected to increase participation of citizens and communities. Such participation can be long-term and/or short-term, more people and/or more contributions, increased quality and/or increased quantity, and increasing participation of specific groups and/or 'anyone'. These strategies specify how to increase self-efficacy, diversity and accessibility, social interaction between citizens, recruitment and project framing, appreciation and importance, and gamification. The advice on how to implement these strategies in practice varies from 'organise a "soft contest": pick up garbage on the way!' to implement gamification, to 'connect to community priorities - for example by focusing on safety of active travel routes rather than pollution' in order to increase diversity and accessibility.

The ACTION Participation Roadmap Tool is intended for project managers of citizen science projects that want to increase participation. A complementary audience consists of researchers working on community engagement and participation in citizen science. The Participation Roadmap Tool will be included in the [ACTION toolkit](#).

This deliverable explains the ACTION Participation Roadmap Tool in more detail, and outlines the methodology that we used to make it. The content of this deliverable is therefore also useful for those who want to develop a similar type of tool.

1 INTRODUCTION

Engaging a community of citizens is at the core of every citizen science project. As we can see in the participatory science lifecycle (figure 1), engaging citizens happens throughout the lifecycle of a citizen science project. It involves attracting a community, and maintaining it.

This deliverable introduces strategies to increase community engagement and practical advice for their implementation. Together, they form the ACTION Participation Roadmap Tool that can be used by the citizen science community for increasing participation. This Participation Roadmap Tool forms the core of this deliverable: we explain this tool (chapter 3), and describe the methodology that we used to make it (chapter 2). In doing so, we build upon our earlier work, where we explain the initial guidelines and tools for community engagement and monitoring in more detail (Janssen et al. 2020).

Figure 1: Participatory science lifecycle

As we explained in the ACTION deliverable 5.4 (Janssen et al. 2020), there are various ways to approach community engagement. We have chosen a practical entry point- that of participation. We consider participation as the practical translation of community engagement: a community that is engaged, participates in the project, and to increase participation is to increase engagement.

Participation in citizen-science projects can be of several types:

- It can be **short-term or long-term participation**. A citizen can solve one folding puzzle on the online platform Zooniverse, or they can count butterflies once a month for nine years.
- Increased participation can mean **more citizens, or more contributions per citizen**. When a project manager wants to increase the number of observations of plastic waste,

they can focus on attracting more volunteers, or on stimulating every volunteer to increase their observations (or both).

- Next to increasing the quantity of participation, a citizen science project might also want to **increase the quality of contributions**, for example by increasing the accuracy of the measurements of air pollution that the citizens record.
- Last, project managers might be interested in **increasing participation of specific groups, rather than of anyone**. For example, a project might want to attract more young people, or increase participation of people living in a specific neighbourhood.

We have used these aspects of participation to structure the strategies for increasing participation in the participation roadmap.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this chapter we outline the research methods that have led to the content and form of the Participation Roadmap Tool. The methodology consisted of five steps. The methods in the first three steps are outlined in more detail in the ACTION deliverable 5.4 (Janssen et al. 2020).

2.1 Literature review

We started with a systematic literature review about why people participate in citizen science projects and on how to increase this participation. The systematic review was based on an article search in SCOPUS using the search terms “citizen science” AND “motivat*” OR “engagement”, additional searches in the journal ‘Citizen Science Practice and Theory’, and by checking cited articles. A total of 156 articles were selected for the review, based on relevance of the topic and novelty of the research.

Analysing these results led us to formulate seven factors that can have a positive or negative impact on participation: self-efficacy, demographics and bias, social factors, feedback, recruitment, task design, and structural barriers.

2.2 Case study of the citizen science work of the Dutch Butterfly Conservation

In addition, we did a case study of the Dutch Butterfly Conservation (DBC) to find out to what extent the framing of a project by DBC has an influence on the citizens’ framing of this project. By framing we mean a way of interpreting and simplifying reality. We hypothesised that the framing of a project could have consequences for whether and how volunteers participate: the project’s framing can attract a certain group of citizens, determine in which way they participate, and for how long.

We first did a framing analysis of DBC’s website by coding it based on a combination of frameworks from Snow and Benford (1988) and Matthes and Kohring (2008). After that, we conducted seven semi-structured interviews with participants of DBC’s citizen science project, asking them about their participation in the project: why they chose to participate, but also why they upheld participation over the years.

From the analysis of the results we concluded that the framing of the project by the DBC organisation overlapped with the reasons and framing used by the participants to explain why they chose to participate. This led us to include *framing* as a factor that can positively or negatively impact participation. For more information see also Groen (2020).

2.3 Workshop round 1 accelerator

During an event organized by ACTION to kick-off its first accelerator programme for the citizen science pilots in February 2020, we validated and extended the strategies for increasing

participation. During the workshop, and based on the preliminary findings of the literature review (see section 2.1.) and case study (see section 2.2.), we presented six strategies for increasing participation: gamification, social interaction, communication, accessibility, collaboration with organisations and institutions, and aligning with community goals.

After presenting the strategies we asked the 12 participants to write down practical examples on how they would implement these strategies in their projects. Then, participants read everyone's examples and marked them for what types of participation (long-term, quality, etc) they thought this example would work best. The results of this workshop verified the strategies, and gave us a list of practical examples on how to implement these strategies.

2.4 Workshop round 2 accelerator

A year later, we held a similar workshop during the ACTION kick-off event for the second accelerator programme for a new round of citizen science pilots. Here, based on a synthesis of the completed literature review, the DBC case study, and feedback from the previous workshop, we presented six strategies: self-efficacy, diversity and accessibility, social interaction between citizens, recruitment and project framing, appreciation and importance, and gamification. Again we asked participants to write down practical examples on how to implement the strategies, and to mark the examples for what type of participation they would work best.

2.5 Workshop ACTION consortium and externals

With the results of the previous steps, we designed a participation roadmap using Miro. This participation roadmap outlines the different types of participation, and connects them to six strategies. The strategies are then attached to several examples of practical implementations. For more information on what this participation roadmap looks like, see chapter 3.

In a workshop for the ACTION consortium and some interested externals, we presented the participation roadmap, and asked participants for feedback and for adding their own practical implementations of the strategies. The roadmap received positive feedback, and more examples were added.

3 PARTICIPATION ROADMAP

The final version of the participation roadmap can be found [here](#) and [on Zenodo](#). This roadmap is openly accessible, and will be linked to in the ACTION toolkit.

Below we will briefly explain how the participation roadmap can be used.

Figure 2: Screenshot of participation roadmap 1

The participation roadmap starts with an explanation of what the tool is, and for which purposes and how to use it (figure 2). It also outlines the different types of participation: long-term versus

short-term, more citizens versus more contributions, quality versus quantity, and specific groups versus anyone.

Figure 3: Screenshot of participation roadmap 2

Depending on the type of participation the user wants to increase, they can follow a line that leads them to the strategies that are best suited for the chosen type of participation (see figure 3 for an overview of the strategies).

Figure 4: Screenshot of participation roadmap 3

Each of the strategies is then briefly explained, and comes with practical advice on how to implement it in a citizen science project (figure 4).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable introduces the ACTION Participation Roadmap tool, which outlines a number of strategies that citizen science projects can use to increase different types of participation in their projects. We introduced six strategies that can increase participation: self-efficacy, diversity and accessibility, social interaction between citizens, recruitment and project framing, appreciation and importance, and gamification. And we relate these strategies to various types of participation which they can impact. These types of participation refer to: long-term and/or short-term, more people and/or more contributions, increased quality and/or increased quantity, and increasing participation of specific groups and/or anyone.

We based the strategies and the actual advice for how to implement them in practice on evidence from a systematic literature study, an in-depth case study of an existing and successful citizen science project, and three interactive workshops. The 'ACTION Participation Roadmap Tool' will be part of ACTION's online toolkit. As participation is at the core of every citizen science project, this deliverable and its associated tool contribute to ACTION's aim of supporting citizen science. Furthermore, since increasing diversity and accessibility is an important strategy for increasing participation, this participation roadmap tool contributes to ACTION's aim of making citizen science more inclusive.

5 REFERENCES

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